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1 EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The APPLICATE Post-Processing Environment provides processing capacity to APPLICATE partners to support analysis of multiple datasets and creation of new combined datasets.

1. INTRODUCTION

The purpose of this report is to describe the APPLICATE Post-Processing Environment. This provides processing capacity to APPLICATE partners to support analysis of multiple datasets and creation of new combined datasets.

This report refers to the online material on the APPLICATE Post-Processing Environment which is available through the [APPLICATE Data Portal](#).

2. Information about the Post-Processing Environment

1.1 Overview

The Post-Processing Environment is based on a small HPC type compute systems containing multiple nodes which all are running Ubuntu Xenial. The post-processing infrastructure provides End-to-End data consistency on network traffic and at disk level. All data are stored lz4 compressed, which in average saves up to 20% of the capacity, depending on the data format.

The system consists of 3 hardware nodes:

- Login system ppi-login-b1.met.no
 - CPU: Intel(R) E5-2650 v2@2.60GHz 16Cores/32Threads, RAM: 65GB
- Compute system 1
 - CPU: Intel(R) E5-2650 v2@2.60GHz 16Cores/32Threads, RAM:192GB
- Compute system 2
 - CPU: Intel(R) E5-2650 v2@2.60GHz 16Cores/32Threads, RAM:256GB

Compute system 1 and 2 are available for batch and interactive jobs via GridEngine.

1.2 Information on how to login

The system can be accessed with the username and from the IP address(es) the APPLICATE partner has provided. The login node allows users to submit jobs to the batch system, which in turn delegates the workload on the compute nodes. In order to get access to the APPLICATE Post-Processing Environment, users has to request access through the [APPLICATE Data Portal](#).

1.3 Filesystem

By default, a user's home directory cannot be accessed by other users. In case a user wants to make data under the home directory readable to other users, the user take the necessary actions to open up the home directory.

The production filesystem is based on Lustre 2.10.1 and is used for processing and simulation workloads. No processing or simulation should be done on the home filesystem as this is not scaled for that purpose.

1.4 Resource Management System

The OpenGridEngine queuing system is used for management of the processing resources. This is useful for distribution of a large number of tasks on a cluster of compute nodes. Using a queuing system has the following advantages:

- **Scheduling**
 - OpenGridEngine allows scheduling of a virtually unlimited amount of work to be performed when resources become available. This means users can

submit as many tasks (or jobs) as they like and the queuing system will ensure proper execution of all of them.

- **Load Balancing**

- OpenGridEngine automatically distributes tasks across the the available processing resources avoiding overloading some components while other are underutilised.

- **Monitoring/Accounting**

- OpenGridEngine monitoring of all submitted jobs and which cluster nodes they're running on, whether they're finished, encountered an error, etc. It also allows querying job history to see which tasks were executed on a given date, by a given user, etc.

Cluster queues are logical groups of hardware that provide certain resources and on which jobs can be executed. When a job is executed by OpenGridEngine, it is placed into a queue which satisfies all the resource requirements of the job.

1.5 Submission of jobs

All jobs require at least one available slot on a compute node in the cluster to run. A slot is equivalent to one core managed by the parallel environment. Submission of jobs is done using `qsub` (batch jobs) or the `qlogin` (interactive jobs) commands. An example of a batch submission is provided below following the syntax of the `qsub` command.

```
qsub -q [queue] -w e -V -N [job_name] -l h_vmem=[memory] -l h_rt=[time] -l
s_rt=[time] -pe shm [n_processors] -o [outputlogfile] -e [errorlogfile]
[pathtoScript] [arg1] [arg2]
```

Example:

```
username@node:~$ qsub -V -b y -cwd -q applicate.q hostname Your job 2585
("hostname") has been submitted
```

- The `-V` option to `qsub` states that the job should have the same environment variables as the shell executing `qsub` (recommended)
- The `-b` option to `qsub` states that the command being executed could be a single binary executable or a bash script. In this case the command `hostname` is a single binary. This option takes a `y` or `n` argument indicating either yes the command is a binary or no it is not a binary.
- The `-cwd` option to `qsub` tells OpenGridEngine that the job should be executed in the same directory that `qsub` was called.
- The 2nd last argument specifies the queue in which the job has to run.
- The last argument to `qsub` is the command to be executed (`hostname` in this case)

optional options:

- `-w e` — verify options and abort if there is an error
- `-N <jobname>` : name of the job
- `-l h_vmem=size` — specify the amount of memory required (e.g. 3G or 3500M) (NOTE: This is memory per processor slot. So if you ask for 2 processors total memory will be 2 X `hvmem_value`)
- `-l h_rt=hh:mm:ss` — specify the maximum run time (hours, minutes and seconds)
- `-l s_rt=hh:mm:ss` — specify the soft run time limit (hours, minutes and seconds) - Remember to set both `s_rt` and `h_rt`

- `-wd <dir>` : Set working directory for this job
- `-j [y/n]` : whether you want to merge output and error log files
- `-m ea` : Will send email when job ends or aborts
- `-P <projectName>` — set the job's project
- `-t <start>-<end>:<incr>` : submit a job array with start index `<start>`, stop index `<end>` in increments using `<incr>`
- `-hold_jid <comma separated list of job-ids, can also be a job id pattern such as 2722*>` : will start the current job/job -array only after completion of all jobs in the comma separated list
- `-hold_jid_ad <job array id, pattern or name>`: will start the current job in a job array only after completion of corresponding job in the job array

The index numbers will be exported to the job tasks via the environment variable `$SGE_TASK_ID`. The option arguments `n`, `m` and `s` will be available through the environment variables `$SGE_TASK_FIRST`, `$SGE_TASK_LAST` and `$SGE_TASK_STEPSIZE`.

Other Options

```

[-a date_time]           request a start time
[-ac context_list]      add context variable(s)
[-ar ar_id]             bind job to advance reservation
[-A account_string]    account string in accounting
record
[-binding [env|pe|set] exp|lin|str]  binds job to processor cores
[-c n s m x]           define type of checkpointing for
job
        n               no checkpoint is performed.
        s               checkpoint when batch server is shut down.
        m               checkpoint at minimum CPU interval.
        x               checkpoint when job gets suspended.
        <interval>     checkpoint in the specified time interval.
[-ckpt ckpt-name]      request checkpoint method
[-clear]               skip previous definitions for job
[-C directive_prefix] define command prefix for job
script
[-dc simple_context_list]  delete context variable(s)
[-dl date_time]          request a deadline initiation time
[-h]                    place user hold on job
[-hard]                 consider following requests "hard"
[-help]                 print this help
[-i file_list]          specify standard input stream
file(s)
[-js job_share]         share tree or functional job share
[-jsv jsv_url]          job submission verification script
to be used
[-masterq wc_queue_list] bind master task to queue(s)
[-notify]               notify job before
killing/suspending it
[-now y[es]|n[o]]      start job immediately or not at
all
[-p priority]           define job's relative priority
[-R y[es]|n[o]]        reservation desired
[-r y[es]|n[o]]        define job as (not) restartable
[-sc context_list]     set job context (replaces old
context)
[-shell y[es]|n[o]]    start command with or without
wrapping <loginshell> -c

```

<code>[-soft]</code>	consider following requests as
<code>soft</code>	
<code>[-sync y[es] n[o]]</code>	wait for job to end and return
<code>exit code</code>	
<code>[-S path_list]</code>	command interpreter to be used
<code>[-verify]</code>	do not submit just verify
<code>[-w e w n v p]</code>	verify mode (error warning none
<code>just verify poke) for jobs</code>	
<code>[-@ file]</code>	read commandline input from file

Notice that the `qsub` command, when successful, will print the job number to `stdout`. You can use the job number to monitor the job's status and progress within the queue as we'll see in the next section.

1.5.1 Example: How to submit a 16 core process

The example below defines a job request with the job name `example`, it will allocate one full node 16 cores for 24 hours to run 16 parallel `mpi` tasks via `mpirun`. Total `vmem` allocation for this job is about `16x500M`.

```
#!/bin/bash -f
#$ -N example
#$ -l h_rt=24:00:00
#$ -pe mpi-fn 16
#$ -l h_vmem=500M
#$ -S /bin/bash
#$ -q ded-parallelx.q
#$ -M username@met.no
#$ -m bae
#$ -o /home/username/OUT_${JOB_NAME}.${JOB_ID}
#$ -e /home/username/ERR_${JOB_NAME}.${JOB_ID}
#$ -R y
# -----

echo "Got $NSLOTS slots."

module add your_software_module (e.g. benchmark/IOR-2.10.3)
module list

mpirun executable parameterfile
```

- `-N example` - job name.
- `-l h_rt=24:00:00` - defines the job runtime. After 24 hours runtime the job will be finished, if it hasn't been finished successfully before.
- `-pe mpi-fn 16` - the variable defines the parallel environment - it must be a multiple of 16 in order to allocate always full nodes exclusively.
- `-q ded-parallel.q` - the variable defines the queue in which the job must run. Currently MET users are allowed to run in the `ded-parallel.q` only.
- `-M username@met.no` - user `username` will get email notifications.
- `-abe` - event notification: job abort, job begin and job end.
- `-o` - specify the job `stdout` directory and file name.
- `-e` - specify the job `stderr` directory and file name.
- `-R y` - enable job reservation.
- `-cwd` – Place the output files (`.e,.o`) in the current working directory.

- -r [y,n] – Should this job be re-runnable (default y)

1.5.2 Example: How to submit 16 programs on 16 CPUs on the same node with parallel execution

The example below defines a job request with a runtime of 120 hours, the job will allocate one full node 16 cores to run 16 parallel tasks via parallel.

```
#!/bin/bash
#$ -S /bin/bash
#$ -l h_rt=120:00:00
#$ -pe mpi 16
#$ -l h_vmem=500M
#$ -q applicate.q
#$ -M username@email
#$ -m abe

echo "Running on $NSLOTS CPUs"
set -x
cd /lustre/store/username/FAUNA/Snap
/usr/bin/parallel -j $NSLOTS ./runSnapTerada.sh -- SnapRun0[0]? >
snapRun00.nohup

exit 0
```

1.5.3 Example: How to submit an array jobs with 2164 single-CPU programs started over the complete system

The example below defines a job-array request. The -t 1-2184 will submit the job 2184 times, each time with a new \$SGE_TASK_ID. It is the task of the user to map the the \$SGE_TASK_ID to a useful task. All jobs can be run in parallel on all available machines. As of the time of writing, it is limited to 200 parallel instances. The -t has to start at a number >= 1.

```
#!/bin/bash
#$ -S /bin/bash
#$ -l h_rt=24:00:00
#$ -q applicate.q
#$ -l h_vmem=500M
#$ -t 1-2184
#$ -o /home/username/OUT_${JOB_NAME}.${JOB_ID}.${HOSTNAME}.${TASK_ID}
#$ -e /home/username/ERR_${JOB_NAME}.${JOB_ID}.${HOSTNAME}.${TASK_ID}

echo "Got $NSLOTS slots for job $SGE_TASK_ID."

./runSnapAllForecasts.pl $SGE_TASK_ID
```

1.5.4 Example: How initiate an interactive job session

The example below defines an interactive job request, it will allocate one full node 16 cores for 1 hour.

```
username@c6220ii-9t58002-bj-compute-ext:~# qlogin -pe mpi 1 -q applicate.q
-l h_vmem=10G
local configuration c6220ii-9t58002-bj-compute-ext.met.no not defined -
using global configuration
Your job 98 ("QLOGIN") has been submitted
waiting for interactive job to be scheduled ...
Your interactive job 98 has been successfully scheduled.
```

Last login: Fri Jan 12 12:18:08 2018 from 157.249.157.82
 username@c6220ii-7t58002-bj-compute-ext:~#

1.6 Software Management System

[Environment Modules](#) is a system for dynamically loading software packages into your environment using a command line tool called module. Software packages are installed in a central location by the APPLICATE support team and then a module file is built for the software which modifies your environment when you load the corresponding module.

1.6.1 How to list available Software Modules

```
~#module avail
```

```
benchmark/IMB-4.1          hdf5/1.8.17
benchmark/IOR-2.10.3-xenial nco/4.6.0
cdo/1.7.2                  nco/4.6.9
ESA-Tools/4.0              netcdf/4.4.1
ESA-Tools/5.0              netcdf/4.5.0
ESA-Tools/6.0pre           netcdf-fortran/4.4.4
ESA-Tools/BRAT-4.0beta     netcdf-fortran/4.5.0
fyba/master                panoply/4.5.1
gdal/2.1.1                 perf/kernel-4.1.13
gdal/2.2.1                 pnetcdf/1.7.0
gdal/python2/2.2.2         pnetcdf/1.9pre
gdal/python3/2.2.2         R/R-3.2.1-met
grib_api/1.16.0            R/R-3.3.1-met
hdf4/4.2.12                R/R-3.4.3-met
hdf5/1.10.1                ...
```

1.6.2 How to get description of a software module

Modules are typically prepending/appending environment variables like \$PATH, \$LD_LIBRARY_PATH to your environment.

Example:

```
~#module show netcdf/4.5.0
```

```
-----
/modules/MET/xenial/GeneralModules/netcdf/4.5.0:
module-whatis      NETCDF 4.5.0
prepend-path       PATH /modules/xenial/NETCDF/4.5.0//bin
prepend-path       LD_LIBRARY_PATH /modules/xenial/NETCDF/4.5.0//lib
prepend-path       --delim  CPPFLAGS -I/modules/xenial/NETCDF/4.5.0//include
prepend-path       --delim  LDFLAGS -L/modules/xenial/NETCDF/4.5.0//lib
module             add hdf5/1.10.1
-----
```

1.6.3 How to load, unload and purge modules

Load a specific version of a module

```
~#module load module_name/version
```

To unload a module

```
~#module unload module_name
```

Purge (clean) the whole module environment

```
~#module purge
```

1.7 EsmValTool

The [Earth System Model eValuation Tool](#) (ESMValTool) is a tool for the evaluation and comparison of Earth System Models (ESMs) and it is installed in the APPLICATE Post-Processing environment.

3. Utilisation in the project

So far the post-processing environment has been underutilised, but usage increased in the spring of 2019. It is also being used for uploading large datasets to the APPLICATE Data Portal for sharing with external communities.

4. SUMMARY

The APPLICATE Post-Processing Environment has been up and running since 1.5 years. It offers processing capacity to partners and allows partners to upload large datasets to the APPLICATE Data Portal.